

**CALCULATION BROUGHT VALUE THE FINAL PRODUCTS PRODUCED
AT THE ENTERPRISES OF THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY IN THE
PROCESS OF MARKETING EVALUATION**

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***Abstract.** The article substantiates that in the current conditions of the economic system, one of the economic goals of production and mining enterprises is to ensure the marketing of their products. This process is closely connected with the economic and geographical position of the country and the situation on the international hydrocarbon market. To do this, the article argues that the sale of oil and gas resources in the form of raw materials or processed products is an economic object that requires more innovation than income-generating sectors of the economy.*

The article shows that the factors affecting the volume of final products must be considered in the process of forecasting oil and gas production while marketing evaluation. To do this, the research paper proposes a method for calculating the cost of final products produced at an oil and gas production facility. The article classifies the factors influencing of the brought value the final products at the enterprises of the

oil and gas industry. When calculating the selling price of products produced in the field of oil and gas production, the uncertainty of measurement data is also considered.

At the end of the article, the prospects for using marketing evaluation methods in stimulating the sale of oil and natural gas and optimizing production are scientifically substantiated.

Studies show that the global market should be researched to apply innovation in terms of practical management, and rational management should be put forward to carry out more efficient production and marketing activities. Regular and correct information is an important factor in this activity. The application of the achievements of scientific and technological progress in production, the aggravation of competition in the domestic and foreign markets, the growing need for operational information in enterprises.

Keywords: *oil and gas business, brought value the final products, raw material cost indicator, marketing of oil and natural gas.*

Formulation of the problem. Let's analyze the features of the development of an oil and gas field and marketing analysis of segments of the field market. When exporting crude oil and natural gas, there are a number of properties and unique characteristics. In the export process, how far these products should be sold, what means of transportation to the geographical point of consumption, including the choice of an advantageous mode of transportation, geographical conditions, frequency of demand, etc. such requirements should be taken into account [5].

Since the uncertainty in the process of estimating the volume of output in many areas of the economy is very small, the estimation of the measurements ε_t can be neglected when constructing the production function [1]. Because the world level of prices for products in these areas is changing with very low dynamics. At the same time, targeted restrictions on the production of these products are rarely used. However, when constructing a production function at the enterprises of the oil and

gas industry, it is necessary to consider the above factors, since they have a great influence on the volume of final products.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The reviewed literature has shown that some researchers have analyzed individual factors that affect the volume of final production in oil and gas production enterprises using different theories. It should be noted that Better M., Cheng L., Modestus O., Liao R.F. the authors conducted research on this issue. However, it became clear from the analysis of the literature that the problem of systematic forecasting of production at oil and gas production enterprises under conditions of information uncertainty still awaits its solution.

The literature reviewed showed that some researchers analyzed the individual factors affecting the volume of the final product in oil and gas production sites using fuzzy set theory.

The purpose and objectives of the article. As we discussed, the method can be used to evaluate the organization of sales in an enterprise. Thus, the cost indicator of raw materials lies at the heart of the oil and gas industry. The problem of pricing manifests itself in terms of sales and production costs. In addition, one of the important issues in the evaluation system is related to the cost of production. This part relates to the calculation and creation of costs at the stages of exploration, production and use of oil and gas [4].

The need for a different methodological justification of costs arises in 3 cases in a phased series:

- The initial stage is directly related to production;
- The second stage is the calculation of the costs associated with processing and transportation;
- Thirdly, the costs associated with the supply and implementation are analyzed.

At all 3 stages, the optimality of the components and rules of production should be clarified, the profitability ratios of the participating enterprises and production

unions should be determined, the economic and political interests of the state should be shown, demonstrating the economic benefit from exports.

The object of the study of marketing activities is the analysis of the parameters of the oil and gas market, the study of promising trends in the indicator of business activity (business activity) of partners, pricing policy, ways to sell oil and gas products, reactions to the emergence of new types of fuel and a number of other oil and gas products and forecasting sales volumes this industry [3].

The oil and gas field has its own characteristics of development, in connection with this, there are features of the marketing analysis of both the market as a whole and its individual segments. For example, the main indicators of the scale of the market are the size of the market and the share of the organization in its composition. The volume of the oil and gas market for a certain period of time characterizes the possible volume of sales of oil and natural gas produced on the local market, as well as the possible volume of sales of refined products of oil and natural gas. At the same time, the prospects for the sale of these products in the domestic and world markets should be taken into account.

Presenting main material. Let us explain, using a practical example, the methodology for calculating the cost of the final product produced at the enterprises of the oil and gas industry in the course of marketing evaluation. For the practical application of the problem, it is necessary to choose a class of functions and parameters ($w=b$, a , A) in such a way as to ensure good equality of indicators. It should be noted that due to the uncertainty of the different origin of the data, it is impossible to completely ensure this equality for all values of Y_t , K_t , L_t . To take into account the uncertainty of modeling and statistics at oil and gas production enterprises, it is necessary to link the model to a regression system of equations that takes into account the additive error. In order to get a more accurate forecast in this area of production, it is necessary to take into account the uncertainty of measurement evaluation:

$$Q = F(K;L;w)+ \varepsilon_t \quad t=\overline{0, T}, \quad (1)$$

where ε_t – represents the uncertainty in the measurement evaluation. Symbolically, the problem of uncertainty in data measurements is called the problem of evaluating data measurements.

However, possibilistic uncertainty related to real-world production data does not allow to use classical regression models. This must be taken into account when establishing the production function in oil and gas production enterprises, since they have a significant impact on the volume of the final product produced.

Thus, the sharp change in the price of oil and gas over the years, the targeted restrictions applied to oil and gas production, create difficulties in establishing a production function that more accurately describes the reality in this area[3]. At the same time, when establishing a production function in this area, one should take into account the uncertainty of the data, their inaccuracy and statistical errors.

In the process of forecasting oil and gas production, it is important to divide the factors affecting the volume of the final product into 2 groups. The first group includes the evaluation of data measurements (ε_t). Examples of this group of factors are changes in the volume of production in accordance with international agreements, significant fluctuations in fuel prices, changes in the exchange rate of the national currency. These types of factors are assessed by adjusting statistical indicators. The second group of factors can often be data uncertainty, their inaccuracy, statistical errors in the assessment of economic events and characteristics. These types of factors can be estimated using fuzzy set theory.

First, let's look at the measurement evaluation (ε_t) factors in the oil and gas production forecasting process.

As noted above, the expected uncertainty in the measurement evaluation is characterized by the first group of influencing factors, which is determined by the formula that we propose below:

$$\varepsilon_t = (H \pm P) \cdot N \cdot K \quad (2)$$

where H is the natural volume of oil and gas exported in the current year; P- due to international agreements, geological factors, etc. the expected changes in the

export of oil (gas); N is -average annual export price of 1 barrel of oil (or 1000 m³ of gas); K-average annual exchange rate of the national currency to 1 US dollar. It should be noted that if the indicators of the current year or previous years are analyzed, then $P = 0$.

Using equations (1) and (2), we can express the nominal value of the final product as follows:

$$Q=Y + \varepsilon_t \text{ or, } Y= Q - \varepsilon_t \quad (3)$$

Y - the reduced value of the product produced.

The study was conducted at the level of an oil and gas company to show practical solutions to the problem. Table 1 shows the technical and economic indicators of the oil and gas production facility used to build the model.

Table 1. Technical and economic indicators of the investigated oil and gas production enterprise (SOCAR)

Years	Amount of oil produced	Average annual price of 1 bar. of oil	Amount of gas produced (in 1000m ³)	Average annual cost of 1000m ³ of gas	Total cost of oil and gas produced (USD)
2007	8800,9	72,7	387239,6	205,5	1055766
2008	8651,3	97,7	380657,2	284,3	1099439
2009	8543,3	61,9	375905,2	126,2	1200078
2010	8459,7	79,6	372226,8	127,2	1245439
2011	8400,9	111	369639,6	129	1291819
2012	8289,8	111,4	364751,2	99,1	1230998
2013	8314,9	108,8	365855,6	143,2	1182075
2014	8320,6	98,9	366106,4	141,04	1081111
2015	8160,6	52,4	359066,4	82,6	1087576
2016	7522,4	44	330985,6	85,5	1083597
2017	7427,1	54,53	326792,4	89,6	1100498
2018	7542,3	72,93	331861,2	85,75	1114527

Y (the reduced value of the product) was calculated using the indicators in table 1 and formulas (3), (2) and is given in Table 2.

Table 2. The brought value the final products of oil and gas produced at the oil and gas production facility

	2007	2008	...	...	2016	2017	2018
The reduced value of the product (Oil) Y_n	387239,6	380657,2	...	...	330985,6	326792,4	331861,2
The reduced value of the product (Gaz) Y_q	495393,5	640364,8	...	...	517637,7	502959,7	539014,6
TOTAL (Y)	882633,1	1021022			848623,3	829752,1	870875,8

The definition of the reduced value of the product allows you to more accurately estimate the real volume of production in value terms. This economic indicator was used in the next section to predict the final product under conditions of uncertain information.

Conclusions and prospects for further development. An important direction in the development of marketing research of oil and gas fields is the process of state regulation aimed at supporting ordinary consumers (legal entities and individuals in various fields) and increasing their effective demand along with specialized oil and gas companies.

An important part of marketing research in oil and gas fields is the assessment of monopoly and the level of competition. At the same time, the number and size of oil and gas companies operating in the market, as well as their market share, are used as indicators characterizing them.

For the oil and gas market, it is mandatory to conduct a marketing analysis of the position of products on the sales market, as well as an analysis of the elasticity of supply and demand[2]. Thus, the volume of sales, the average price level, the income received from the sale of products, the amount of profit received, taking into account the influence of various internal and external factors, depend on them.

Speaking about ways to improve marketing activities at oil and gas producing enterprises and departments, a number of measures should be taken. An important task of oil and gas marketing is the organization of timely production of oil and natural gas as a result of the economic and financial activities of the enterprise, as

well as the creation of a systemic connection between the sale of oil and natural gas, as well as the proportional distribution of the needs of industrial and production areas in oil and natural gas in connection with technical development.

The results of the study showed that when calculating the volume of final products at the enterprises of the oil and gas industry, it is necessary to take into account the specifics of this industry. First, the realized value of products produced in the area should be calculated, taking into account the uncertainty of the measurement data. Determining the selling *of the brought value products* allows you to more accurately assess the actual volume of production in value terms.

Analysis of the calculation of the volume of the final product inside oil and gas production enterprises in the context of uncertain information showed that the impact factors must be properly assessed. In order to get a more accurate forecast in this area of production, it is necessary to take into account the uncertainty of measurement evaluation.

References:

1. Akhundov V.J., Mammadova S.K. and Aliyev A.M. "Investigation of the "Input-output" model of the Azerbaijani economy in interval information conditions." 13th International Conference on Theory and Applications of Fuzzy Systems and Soft Computing ICAFS 2018(Indexed by Web of Science and Scopus) 27-28 August, Warsaw, Poland, 2018.
2. Bui M. T., Nguyen H. M., Determinants Affecting Profitability of Firms: A Study of Oil and Gas Industry in Vietnam, The Journal of Asian Finance , volume 8 , issue 1 , p. 599 - 608 Posted: 2021
3. Davis, S. J. & Haltiwanger, J. Sectoral job creation and destruction responses to oil price changes. Journal of monetary economics, 48(3), 465-512, 2001.
4. Campbell, John M., et al Analysis and Management of Petroleum Investments Campbell Petroleum Service, Norman, Oklahoma, 1992.

5. Cousins (Paul), Lamming (Richard), Lawson (Benn), and Squire (Brian):
“Strategic Supply Management Principles, Theories and Practice”, Pearson
Education, UK, 2008.